

**INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE BLOOM TAXONOMY METHOD IN
MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES**

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Abstract

The article presents an analysis of theoretical data and practical tasks related to the application of Bloom's taxonomy during the teaching of chemistry in medical universities of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Keywords: Bloom's taxonomy, knowledge, pedagogical goals, synthesis and analysis, independent work, practical exercises.

The primary objective of the modern education sphere is to shape and develop a well-rounded individual prepared for the dynamic changes in the economy, politics, legal, and social domains. This individual should meet contemporary requirements in terms of education, intellectuality, spirituality, and morality. Currently, the Republic of Kazakhstan has laid conceptual foundations for the ongoing development, reform, and modernization of all public activity sectors, including the education system. The continued reliance on established pedagogical methods in the educational process could impede active learning. The constant elevation of standards in the face of global competition creates ample opportunities for the application of modern pedagogical technologies in the learning process. In order to coordinate the interaction between teachers and students in line with the concept of subject relations, emphasizing the harmonious development of the integral personality of the student in a holistic educational process [1].

One of the pressing issues is defining a conceptual and scientific approach to the theory, trends, structure, and functions of processes in the pedagogical system. This should be done with reference to modern methodology, a new pedagogical paradigm, and both foreign and domestic experiences, aiming to optimize processes within the education system.

The materials provided are classified into six levels in accordance with the specified cognitive theory to foster higher-order thinking skills. The development of educational materials aligned with Bloom's levels enhances the effectiveness of the educational process and stimulates the independent work of students [2].

The study aims to assess the effectiveness of Bloom's taxonomy in the educational process in medical universities.

Research objectives:

Preparation of tasks based on Bloom's taxonomy levels, designed to cultivate higher-order thinking skills in students during theoretical and practical chemistry classes.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of tasks developed according to Bloom's taxonomy levels in cultivating the functional literacy of students.

Research methods and materials: The systematic nature of the pedagogical design process is grounded in the application of the research method in the educational and practical activities of chemical disciplines within the cognitive framework of Bloom's taxonomy. This approach fully achieves educational goals by precisely structuring the list of cognitive learning activities. Today, the most common and proven taxonomy in the learning process is the traditional Bloom taxonomy.

Bloom's taxonomy is a variant of the classification of pedagogical goals, proposed by a group of scientists led by Benjamin Bloom in 1956. The initial version aimed to standardize methods for measuring and evaluating knowledge and learning skills in university practice. Bloom's taxonomy classifies mental actions into six levels: from knowledge, understanding, and application of knowledge to analysis, synthesis, and evaluation [3,4].

First-year students enrolled in the medical education program of the South Kazakhstan Medical Academy engage in didactic tasks during chemistry lessons in a basic disciplines cycle, performing educational tasks—both theoretical and practical, laboratory work based on competencies and learning outcomes. These tasks train students to think critically, act, explore, and be independent, utilizing theoretical material based on Bloom's taxonomy to ensure the development of students' personalities.

Here is a detailed description of the classification of the six levels of cognition in accordance with this version of the taxonomy.

The first level is "knowledge" - where memorization and reproduction of the studied material take place, and the student knows the terminology, facts, methods, and basic concepts. The second level is "understanding" - the criterion for assimilation at this level is the

ability to interpret the material, predict expected consequences and results. The student understands facts, principles, and can create diagrams, diagrams, and graphs. The third level is "application" - at this cognitive stage, the student can use the acquired material in practical work, characterized by the adequate application of methods, principles, and tools. The fourth level is "analysis" - here positive extrapolation occurs, and the student, based on previously acquired knowledge, discovers new information, identifies interrelated parts, preserves the structure of the organization as a whole, corrects mistakes, and identifies cause and effect. The fifth level is "synthesis" - this level involves combining elements into a single whole, having novelty and originality (scientific research, systematization, classification, reporting, case study construction, etc.). The sixth level - "evaluation" - is defined as the culmination of mastering the previous stages. Here, the student must have the ability to draw cognitive conclusions and suggestions and apply them in certain practical situations. These levels are often represented in the form of the well-known "pyramid of flowering."

The first level is "knowledge" - here, memorization and reproduction of the studied material take place;

the student knows the terminology, facts, methods, and basic concepts. The second level is "understanding" - the criterion of assimilation at this level is the ability to interpret (interpret, present) the material, as well as predict the expected consequences and results. The student understands the laws, facts, principles, and can create diagrams and graphs.

To reflect the stated theoretical provisions, the authors have developed questions and tasks on the discipline "Chemistry" for 1st-year students of the South Kazakhstan Medical Academy in accordance with Bloom's taxonomy and implemented during practical classes.

Research results and their discussion. Based on the proposed Bloom taxonomy, research was conducted to verify the impact on the degree of mastering educational material by students on some topics of the discipline "Chemistry." For 1st-year students enrolled in the medical educational program in the discipline "Chemistry," research work was carried out on the basis of questions and tasks developed in accordance with the conditions of the method. A control group of 25 students and an experimental group of 25 students were selected.

Diagram 1.

On the basis of the Bloom pyramid, questions and tasks on the levels of cognition on the topic "Colligative properties of solutions" were developed in accordance with the calendar thematic plan (Table 1). First, the initial levels of knowledge of both groups were checked using test tasks, and the results were almost the same (1,2- levels in the diagram). At the end of the experiment, the knowledge levels of the students in both groups were checked by passing test tasks at an intermediate control. According to the results of the interim control, it was found that the average qualitative indicator of the experimental group, in which Bloom's taxonomy was used, was higher compared to the control

group (3,4 - levels in the diagram). The results of the observations are presented below in the form of a diagram (Diagram 1).

According to the results of the study, it was found that the students of the experimental group had increased interest in the subject and the dynamics of cognitive activity. In the questionnaire received from the students of the experimental and control groups, thoughts and opinions were expressed about the development of educational material based on this applied pedagogical technology.

Table 1.

№	Bloom's Taxonomy Levels	Developed questions and tasks
1.	Know	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are solutions and their classification. 2. Specify the ways to express the concentrations of solutions. 3. What are the colligative properties of solutions? 4. Define the degree of dissociation, electrolytes and nonelectrolytes. 5. Define Raoul's law. 6. Define the phenomenon of osmosis and propose an equation for calculating osmotic pressure. 7. Name isotonic, hypertensive and hypotonic solutions. 8. What are cryoscopic and ebullioscopic constants?
2.	Understand	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Explain what tasks can be solved using the colligative properties of solutions in medical practice. 2. Why solutions of electrolytes and nonelectrolytes have different electrical conductivity, give examples. 3. Explain the occurrence of osmotic pressure and characterize hypotonic, isotonic and hypertonic solutions. 4. Describe the increase in boiling point and decrease in freezing point of solutions, following Raoul's law. 5. The processes of hemolysis and plasmolysis occur in biological fluids of a living organism, depending on the number of concentrations of dissolved matter. Explain the physiological basis of these processes.
3.	Use	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In medical practice, a 0.9% isotonic NaCl solution is utilized, with osmotic pressure equivalent to blood plasma. Perform the necessary calculations and prepare a 0.9% isotonic NaCl solution using chemical equipment and utensils. 2. When injecting a hypotonic solution into the blood, endosmosis occurs inside red blood cells. This can cause the cells to swell and their membranes to rupture, leading to hemolysis. Consequently, prepare a 0.25 M glucose solution and determine whether its osmotic pressure is hypotonic compared to the osmotic pressure in human blood. 3. Small quantities of a hypertonic solution injected into the human body can cause erythrocytes to lose water, reducing in volume and undergoing shrinkage (plasmolysis) due to exosmosis. Accordingly, prepare a 0.5 M glucose solution and demonstrate that human blood is hypertonic compared to osmotic pressure. 4. Determine the temperature at which a 40% solution of ethyl alcohol freezes, considering that water undergoes crystallization at 0°C, transforming into ice. 5. Identify the boiling point of a 50% sucrose solution; considering that water boils at 100°C, it transitions into steam. 6. By utilizing the cryoscopic method, if the freezing point of water decreases by 1 degree upon dissolving 18 g of a substance in 100 g of water, determine the molecular weight of the dissolved substance.
4.	Analyse	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When a hypotonic solution enters the blood, red blood cells increase in volume and the process of hemolysis occurs, and when a hypertonic solution is injected into the blood, on the contrary, it leads to the process of plasmolysis. Describe these two phenomena relatively. 2. In surgery, hypertensive bandages soaked in 10% NaCl solution are used to treat purulent wounds. Explain the effect of a hypertensive bandage, following the law of osmosis. 3. Animal and plant cells consist of a surface layer of protoplasm with the ability to form a semipermeable membrane. Analyze why, when you put this cell in an isotonic solution, the volume is preserved and works normally. 4. When cutting a lemon with a sharp knife, the juice does not stand out, and if you sprinkle lemon with sugar, the juice will start to come out. How to explain this phenomenon. 5. The human body needs 8-10 g of salt daily. Analyze the biological effect of salt in the body by referring to the phenomenon of osmosis. 6. Comparably explain the increase in boiling points and decrease in freezing temperatures of electrolyte and non-electrolyte solutions compared to pure water, following Raoul's law.

5.	Synthesize	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What kind of pain is observed when the osmotic blood pressure deviates from normal. 2. Bacterial cells exhibit higher osmotic pressure. Predict the effects on the human body when antibiotic drugs are injected into these cells. 3. Prepare a glucose solution that matches the osmolarity of a 0.9% isotonic sodium chloride solution. 4. Identify similarities and distinctive features in determining the osmotic pressure of electrolyte and nonelectrolyte solutions. 5. Formulate the significance of osmotic pressure for a living organism. 6. What recommendations can you provide to maintain normal osmotic pressure of fluids in the human body?
6.	Estimate	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assess how future doctors will apply the acquired knowledge about the colligative properties of solutions in their medical practice. 2. Evaluate the similarities and differences between the phenomena of osmosis and reverse osmosis. 3. When erythrocyte cells are placed in solutions of different concentrations, the phenomena of hemolysis and plasmolysis occur. Provide a comparative assessment of the conditions under which these phenomena occur. 4. Explain which solutions exhibit higher or lower boiling and freezing points compared to pure water and identify the factors on which it depends. 5. Predict the consequences if the amount of protein decreases due to prolonged starvation of the human body or deterioration of kidney function.

Thus, it is proved that in the educational process in medical universities of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the proposed tasks on the levels of Bloom's taxonomy in the discipline "Chemistry" contribute to the practical application of the acquired knowledge of students, increase functional literacy, form higher thinking skills, develop the ability of critical thinking, improve cognitive and cognitive knowledge.

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